

ESTIMATION OF LEVELS OF PLASMA CHLORIDE USING BLOOD GAS MEASUREMENTS

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Abstract:

Purpose: Chloride is the main plasma anion. There are several methods for determining serum chloride levels. Unfortunately, these methods are sometimes not available in urgent mode, in which values are needed. Here we describe the formula for estimating plasma chloride levels.

Place and Duration: In the Department of Emergency Medicine, Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi in collaboration with physiology department for six months duration from September 2019 to February 2020.

Methods: 52 consecutive patients were enrolled in the study and were assessed for serum chloride levels using the formula $CL^- = (Na^+ + 10 - TBB)$ and also directly measured by colorimetry. The correlation between these two values was analyzed using the Pearson correlation coefficient, and the agreement was shown on the Bland-Altman chart.

Results: Comparison of values obtained by estimation and laboratory determination of plasma chloride showed a significant correlation ($r = 0.97$). Consistent compliance has been described under -4.8 and $+6.6$ on the Bland-Altman chart during measurements.

Conclusion: the formula presented here can be a reliable alternative to direct measurement of serum chloride when direct results are not available.

Key words: Arterial blood gas (ABG), Total Buffer Base (TBB), Anion gap (AG), Serum Chloride

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INTRODUCTION:

Chloride is the most important anion associated with an additional sodium cellular liquid with a normal concentration of 96 to 106. It is not possible to fully interpret alkaline acid disorders without knowing the concentration of chloride in serum. In the quantitative analysis of acid-base pH in plasma, three arguments are determined: $p\text{CO}_2$, total concentration of weak non-volatile acids and strong ion difference (SID)¹⁻². On the other hand, bicarbonate (HCO_3) concentration is considered to be SID-dependent. It is suggested that chloride is the main electrolyte that defines SID and therefore directly affects acid base disorders in the clinical environment. In addition, serum chloride levels were associated with mortality rates in some patient groups and were suggested as a predictive factor³⁻⁴. Therefore, it is very important to determine the timely and correct concentration of chloride in the serum for decisions in the emergency department. Different methods are defined for the measurement of se-rum chlorides⁵. The colometric titration method uses electrolysis current to measure ion formation, while ion-selective electrode uses a converter to convert ion activity into an electrical potential that can be measured using a voltmeter or pH-meter. The colorimetric method combines chloride with other elements to form a color solution and then measures the color density to determine the chloride concentration⁵⁻⁶. For selective measurement of chloride ions, cyclic voltammetry of the Ag electrode was also defined. These methods have been defined for years, and their complexity, cost and accuracy vary, but even today compliance with serum chloride levels is not available as a 24-hour new test. To solve this problem, we explain the formula for calculating serum chloride levels using information available in the emergency environment through blood gas analysis⁶⁻⁷.

METHODS:

This study was held in the Department of Emergency Medicine in collaboration with physiology department of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi for six months duration from September 2019 to February 2020.

In this study the authors developed a practical formula based on known acid-base physiology. Then we predicted Cl^- concentration in 52 consecutive patients in the emergency department for which Cl^- concentration had been ordered by the treating physician. For each patient, three simultaneous samples were collected: One complete blood count tube, one clot sample for serum collection, and one arterial blood gas analysis heparinized sample. Serum Hb, electrolytes and blood gas analysis were derived

from these samples. The results derived from the formula were compared with the biochemical report of the chlorine sample from the laboratory. Correlation was analyzed using the Pearson coefficient and agreement described in the Bland-Altman plot. The Stewart physicochemical approach to acid-base interpretation takes into account all the cations and anions that play a role in plasma electroneutrality (11). The plasma remains electrically neutral in physiologic and pathologic conditions through the equilibration of total cations with total anions. The concept is summarized in the formula below in which A- represents serum albumin, phosphorus, and other negatively charged proteins: Strong ion difference (mmol/L) = $[\text{Na}^+] + [\text{K}^+] + [\text{Ca}^{2+}] + [\text{Mg}^{2+}] - [\text{Cl}^-]$ [Strong ion difference] - $[\text{A}^-] = [\text{HCO}_3^-] + [\text{CO}_3^{2-}] + [(\text{OH}^-)] - [\text{H}^+]$ The equation for SID - $[\text{A}^-]$ can be reduced to approximately $[\text{HCO}_3^-]$ because $[\text{HCO}_3^-]$ is much greater than $[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{OH}^-]$, and $[\text{CO}_3^{2-}]$. In addition, if one replaces the normal values for these concentrations in a physiologic state as shown in Table 1, several conclusions can be made: Since variations in K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentrations are trivial and their influence in the formula adds up to a total of approximately 10 meq/L we replace them with this value. Also we refer to the accumulative concentration of ($\text{Co}_3 \text{H}^- + \text{Po}_4 \text{H}^- + \text{Alb} + \text{Hb} + \text{others}$) as total buffer base (TBB). Then the following formula can be rewritten: $(\text{Na}^+ + 10) = (\text{Cl}^- + \text{TBB})$ and finally $\text{Cl}^- = (\text{Na}^+ + 10) - \text{TBB}$ Box 1 summarizes these formulas. Chloride was measured in a simultaneously collected serum sample. Care was taken for the serum to be extracted immediately after sample collection to limit alterations caused by cell metabolism. An automated colorimetric method was used. Chlorine was measured using colorimetric method by Randex kit, UK with $\text{Cl}^- 5526 \times 100 \text{ mc}$, Reagent $\text{G} \times 100 \text{ mc}$ 2STd $11 \times 5 \text{ mg}$ 3ST, $1 \times 5 \text{ mg}$. The chemical reaction led to the creation of ferric thiocyanate, a brown colored complex. The mixture was left to sit at 37°C for 270 seconds. The density of this substance was then measured using spectrophotometry at 505 nm wavelength compared to a standard sample which revealed the concentration of chloride. Although relatively simple, when available, the test was usually reported over 2-hours after sample collection in the emergency setting. For practical purposes we chose a sample size according to the formula. Fifty-two sequential patients were enrolled, 33 male and 19 females. There was no limitation on the condition for which the test was ordered. In our study, patients suffered from varying disorders such as diabetic ketoacidosis, acute renal failure, chronic kidney disease, intoxication, gastroenteritis, suspected electrolyte or acid-base disturbances.

Box 1. Formula summary

$Na+K+Ca+Mg=Cl+CO_3+Protein+Hb+PO_4$
 $K+Ca+Mg=Unmeasurable\ cation\ \approx 10\ mmol$
 $Protein+Hb+PO_4 = Unmeasurable\ anion$
 $HCO_3+Protein+Hb+PO_4 = TBB$
 $Na+10 = Cl+TBB$
 $Cl = Na+10-TBB$
 $Anion\ gap=UA-UC=Na-(Cl+CO_3)$
 $Anion\ gap=UA-UC=Na-(Na+10-TBB+CO_3)$
 $Aniongap=TBB-(CO_3+10)$

RESULTS:

A total of 52 patients were included in the study. Two chloride values were available for each case: one by calculation and the other by direct biochemical measurement using an automated colorimetric method. Fig. 1 shows the compatibility between these two methods using the Bland-Altman chart. This diagram shows the difference between the values obtained using the formula and laboratory and the average of these two values and shows the proximity of two methods in the entire range of measurements obtained. In addition, the Pearson coefficient was used to measure the statistical correlation between these two values and a correlation coefficient $r = 0.94$ was achieved, which indicates a perfect correlation of both methods.

Na⁺ 142 meq/L	Cl⁻ 103 meq/L
K ⁺ 4.3 meq/L	Co ₃ H ⁻ 25 meq/L
Ca ⁺⁺ 4 meq/L	Po ₄ H ⁻ 2 meq/L
Mg ⁺⁺ 2 meq/L	Proteins 16 meq/L
	Others (So ₄ H ⁻ , Lactate) 6 meq/L
Total: 152 meq/L	Total: 152 meq/L

DISCUSSION:

Chloride is an important non-cellular anion with a proven effect on the state of acid in the body. Although direct measurement is the best method for determining cl concentration, sometimes it is not an operation in an emergency environment⁷⁻⁸. Here we have defined a formula that predicts serum cl levels with a strong core analysis factor with the colorimetric method used as a reference value. There are several methods in the laboratory for the safety of chloride levels, such as autoanalyzer (colorimetric method), coulometric method, mercurial method and specific method of ion chloride electrode⁹⁻¹⁰. Among them, the color method is considered simple and can be done with automatic devices. Since this is the method available in our center, we use the colorimetric method as a reference value. Unfortunately, despite the importance of determining chloride concentrations, this test is not available at closed hours at our center and welcomes the use of an alternative formula for this purpose¹¹⁻¹². This is not the first time that calculated formulas have been used instead of measuring the direct plasma concentration. Rees and others described a computerized formula to predict O₂ arteries press safes using data obtained by analyzing blood acorn samples. Another example of using formulas to predict hard-to-obtain values is an estimate of the rate of glomerular filtration. These formulas help you make quick decisions when there is no option to expect pout directly again. Chloride

measurement is necessary not only for an etiological assessment of the condition of alkaline acid, but also for the classification of the condition and the choice of a common emergency situation for treatment (i.e. salt-sensitive or salt-resistant metabolic alkalosis or normal and high metabolic alkalosis [AG] metabolic acidosis)¹³. Therefore, in cases where direct measurement of chloride is not performed as a matter of urgency, our formula is well correlated with a hand- tentative, which can help in directing urgent patient management. As you can see in the Bland-Altman table, almost all cases associated with this study have been drawn up in a different range of ial between negative and positive 5 mg/dl. These measurements are generally considered acceptable in a clinical environment of 5 mg/dl meaning it is less different. Moreover, this agreement is consistent in terms of measurements taken without much bias at both ends of the story. Pearson's impressive coefficient further increases the relationship between the values obtained from both methods. When there are no chloride levels, our formula can be developed to predict AG¹⁴⁻¹⁵.

CONCLUSION:

The formulas presented in this document are an accurate and acceptable alternative to the direct measurement of serum chloride levels in cases where there is no direct analysis.

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